

Impact of pesticides on marine coral reef foraminifera

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Abstract

Our laboratory study looked into how pesticides affect the foraminifera species *Heterostegina depressa* and their obligatory algal endosymbionts. We incubated the foraminifera separately with different types of pesticides at varying concentrations (1%, 0.01% and 0.0001%); we included the insecticide Confidor© (active substance: imidacloprid), the fungicide Pronto©Plus (tebuconazole), and the herbicide Roundup© (glyphosate). Our evaluation focused on the symbiont's photosynthetically active area (PA), and the uptake of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and nitrogen (nitrate) to determine the vitality of the foraminifera. Our findings showed that even the lowest doses of the fungicide and herbicide caused irreparable damage to the foraminifera and their symbionts. While the insecticide only deactivated the symbionts (PA = 0) at the highest concentration (1%), the fungicide, and herbicide caused complete deactivation even at the lowest levels provided (0.0001%). The fungicide had the strongest toxic effect on the foraminiferal host regarding reduced isotope uptake. In conclusion, all pesticides had a negative impact on the holosymbiont, with the host showing varying degrees of sensitivity towards different types of pesticides.

1. Introduction

1.1. General introduction

30 Coral reefs are some of the most vital marine ecosystems in terms of biomass production,
31 biodiversity, and carbon sequestration. However, they are highly susceptible to the effects
32 of climate change (Wernberg et al., 2013), which is directly related to the accumulation of
33 pesticides (Ukhurebor et al., 2020). Large benthic foraminifera (LBF) are commonly found in
34 coral reefs and are significant contributors to carbonate precipitation and sediment
35 production (Hallock 1981; Prazeres and Renema, 2019). The foraminiferal communities of
36 coral reefs are used as bioindicators of the health of coral reefs through the 'Foraminifera in
37 Reef Assessment and Monitoring' (FORAM) index. This index depends on a quantitative
38 composition of the assemblage, representing three functional groups of foraminifera, i.e.
39 symbiont-bearing foraminifera (LBF), and smaller opportunistic and other heterotrophic
40 foraminifera (Hallock et al., 2003). According to Hallock et al., (2003), LBFs are highly
41 suitable for monitoring the condition of coral reefs, as foraminifera and corals both host
42 phototrophic protists (diatoms, dinoflagellates) as endosymbionts (zooxanthellae).
43 Therefore, they have similar environmental and water-quality requirements. Reef
44 foraminifera are small and highly abundant organisms, making it easy to obtain a statistically
45 significant sample, while collecting them has only minimal impact on the coral reef
46 resources (Hallock et al., 2003; Natsir and Subkhan, 2021). LBFs are known to produce tests
47 made mainly of calcite (CaCO₃) with complex internal and external structures (e.g., Hallock
48 et al., 1991; Hohenegger, 2011; Hottinger, 2006). Those LBFs with increased Mg²⁺ contents
49 (high-Mg calcite) in their tests are particularly important for coral reefs as they serve as a
50 buffer against pH-fluctuations after death (Yamamoto et al., 2012). LBFs have an extended
51 test size, a complex chamber arrangement, and ultrastructural alterations to optimize their
52 symbiosis with microalgae, as well as bacteria (including cyanobacteria) (Hottinger 2006;
53 Hohenegger, 2011; Bernhard et al., 2012). The endosymbionts are obligatory for the LBFs.
54 Even if some LBFs are mixotrophic, they are not able to survive over longer periods without
55 their phototrophic symbionts (Lee, 2006).

56

57 1.2. Foraminifera as an indicator of polluted environments

58 Foraminiferal assemblages are highly sensitive to changes in physical parameters, such as
59 habitat depth, light supply, and water motion (Baker et al., 2009). Previous studies have
60 shown that the metabolism of foraminifera is influenced by changes in food supply, salinity,

61 or light intensity (e.g., Lintner et al., 2020; 2021a). The structure of foraminiferal
62 communities also reflects the state of heavy metal pollution (Ferraro et al., 2006), the
63 toxicity of heavy metals being dependent on the type of metal. Lintner et al. (2021b)
64 discovered that Pb^{2+} did not have a detrimental impact on the metabolism of foraminifera,
65 even at a concentration more than 500 times higher than natural porewater, while a much
66 smaller increase of Cu^{2+} (around 5-fold) resulted in a rapid stop of their carbon assimilation.
67 Ferraro et al. (2006) made similar findings on smaller benthic foraminifera, listing Hg^{2+} as
68 one of the most toxic metals for foraminifera. None of these studies considered LBF,
69 although their presence/absence, vitality, and activity may be used to detect chemical
70 contaminants in seawater. According to Lintner et al. (2022), LBF is highly sensitive to
71 seawater pollution with sunscreens, as demonstrated by the deterioration of the
72 photosynthetic performance of their symbionts as a proxy for environmental
73 contamination.

74 A significant portion of ocean contamination comes from intensive agriculture. Pesticides
75 commonly used in intensive agriculture are transported in rivers and ultimately discharged
76 into the ocean (e.g., Shaw et al., 2010). Additionally, airborne pesticides, partly transported
77 adsorbed to aerosols, enter the ocean via offshore winds. Approximately 1-2% of the total
78 mass of pesticides is transported by such processes and deposited directly into the ocean
79 (Kookana et al., 1998). Depending on rainfall, this value can even increase to over 10%
80 (Baker et al., 1978). Nowadays, a significant proportion of organic pollutants are found in
81 nearshore sediments, as well as in coastal and estuarine plants and animals (e.g., Haynes et
82 al., 2000). Sediment concentrations of pesticides that inhibit photosynthesis can reach up to
83 10 ng L^{-1} , and organophosphates can reach up to $50\text{-}1000\text{ ng L}^{-1}$ (Lewis et al., 2009; Rohde et
84 al., 2006). Shaw et al. (2010) investigated nearshore and offshore areas of the Great Barrier
85 Reef and discovered nearshore pesticide concentrations of approximately 3.8 ng L^{-1} (dry
86 season) and $2.2\text{--}6.4\text{ ng L}^{-1}$ (wet season). Offshore pesticide concentrations were below the
87 detection limit, although two rivers discharging into the sea near the Great Barrier Reef had
88 pesticide concentrations of 350 ng L^{-1} (Shaw et al., 2010). Recent studies by Wang et al.,
89 (2022) mentioned $9.5\text{-}267\text{ ng pesticides L}^{-1}$ seawater in the Yellow Sea and East China Sea
90 which are comparable with values from the last decade. Zhang et al., (2022) investigated a
91 transect along the western Pacific to the Southern Ocean and measured the concentration

92 of 221 different pesticides. Twenty-seven pesticides were detected as highly frequent (>50%
93 of the samples) and one of the dominant substances was tebuconazole which is the active
94 ingredient of Pronto©Plus (the fungicide used in this study).

95 Pesticides will increasingly be applied to reduce pest in cultivation areas due to climate
96 change, which causes shifts in temperature and precipitation in most regions of the world
97 (Delcour et al., 2015). Ukhurebor et al. (2021) found a direct connection between climate
98 change and pesticides, which may ultimately lead to higher concentrations of pesticides
99 being used in agriculture in future. The pesticides are released into the environment, finally
100 entering the food web (Ukhurebor et al., 2020).

101 In this study, we investigated the impact of pesticide pollution on the activity of the LBF
102 *Heterostegina depressa* d'Orbigny 1826 that hosts diatoms. *H. depressa* is used as a model
103 LBF for laboratory studies since the 70s (Röttger, 1972, 1976). We screened three frequently
104 applied pesticides (one herbicide, one insecticide, and one fungicide) at three concentration
105 levels to test their effect on the photosymbiont performance of LBFs. If successful, the
106 presence or absence of LBFs may be used as a proxy for pesticide pollution in marine
107 environments.

108

109 **2. Material and Methods**

110 2.1. Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation (PAM) fluorometry

111 Experiments were performed in six-well plates, each filled with 10 ml sterile filtered artificial
112 seawater (salinity of 38) with a single individual placed in each well. Well-plates were
113 incubated at 25 °C at a light: dark-cycle of 16:8h (30 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Treatments were
114 either pure artificial seawater (control), or seawater enriched with the respective pesticides
115 (active ingredients in brackets): 1%, 0.01%, and 0.0001% equivalent to 10 g L⁻¹, 0.1 g L⁻¹ and
116 0.001 g L⁻¹ Roundup© (herbicide, active ingredient glyphosate); 1%, 0.01%, and 0.0001%
117 Pronto©Plus (fungicide, active ingredient tebuconazole); or 0.1%, 0.001% and 0.00001%
118 which is equivalent to 1 g L⁻¹, 0.01 g L⁻¹, 0.0001 g L⁻¹ Confidor© (insecticide, active ingredient
119 imidacloprid). Commonly applied pesticide concentrations in agriculture are 1% (10 g L⁻¹) for
120 the herbicide and fungicide, respectively, and 1 g L⁻¹ (0.1%) for the insecticide. Since

121 Confidor© is a powder, the information is provided in g L⁻¹, the other pesticides
122 (Roundup©, Pronto©Plus) are liquids and were diluted according to the above information.
123 The selected pesticides are very common in agriculture; maximum concentrations applied
124 were adjusted to concentrations typically used in greenhouses, while the two lower
125 concentrations considered the dilution effects of seawater. The active substances are
126 present in the pesticides in the following concentrations: 1% glyphosate in Roundup©,
127 13.6% tebuconazole in Pronto©Plus and 20% imidacloprid in Confidor©. For each
128 substance, time and concentration level, six replicates were prepared (in total 360
129 measurements). *Heterostegina depressa* are cultivated in a permanent culture at the
130 Department of Palaeontology (University of Vienna) at a constant temperature of 25°C, a
131 salinity of 38 PSU, and light intensity at 30 μmol photons m⁻²s⁻¹ for a 8h-16h light/dark
132 rhythm. These conditions were taken during the experiments.

133 We measured the photosynthetic performance of the photosymbionts for two weeks at
134 days 1, 3, 5, 7 and 14 using variable chlorophyll fluorescence imaging of photosystem II (PSII;
135 Imaging PAM Microscopy Version–Walz GmbH; excitation at 620 nm). Measurement of the
136 variable fluorescence over the maximum quantum yield fluorescence (Fv/Fm) estimates the
137 efficiency of photosystem II (Parkhill et al., 2001). Fv/Fm serves as a proxy for the vitality of
138 the photosymbionts (Parkhill et al., 2001) and therefore it can be used as an indicator of the
139 health of the foraminifera themselves (Hallock et al., 2003). Images from PAM microscopy
140 were taken using the software WinControl-3 (Walz GmbH). Photosynthetic area and total
141 area of each specimen were measured and calculated with the software Image J (version
142 1.53 k, Java). To test for significant effects of pesticides on the photosynthetic activity of the
143 foraminifera, two-way repeated measurement ANOVAs (level of significance p = 0.05) were
144 run to test the effect of pesticide concentration, time, and their interaction. Statistical tests
145 were run with Past 4.03 (Hammer et al., 2001).

146 2.2. Isotopic uptake

147 Incubation experiments took place in crystallization dishes filled with 280 ml sterile filtered
148 artificial seawater. The foraminifera were incubated in pure seawater and in pesticide-
149 amended seawater, respectively. We applied the same pesticides and incubation times as in
150 the photosynthetic performance experiments. The lowest pesticide concentration was
151 excluded because PAM fluorometry experiments showed comparable results to the control.

152 All culture media were enriched with isotopically labelled inorganic nitrogen and carbon
153 ($\text{Na}^{15}\text{NO}_3$, $\text{Na}_2^{13}\text{CO}_3$) to a final concentration of 0.2 mM ^{15}N and ^{13}C (Lintner et al., 2023). For
154 each incubation time (1, 3, 5, and 7 days), foraminifera were placed in dishes and incubated
155 (one per dish, six replicates for each concentration, type of pesticide, and incubation time).
156 After incubation, the foraminifera were rinsed with distilled water and transferred to pre-
157 weighted tin (Sn) capsules. Foraminifera were then dried for three days at room
158 temperature and thereafter decalcified by the addition of 12.5 μl 2 M HCl. After re-drying at
159 50°C for three days, each individual was weighed to the nearest hundreds of milligrams,
160 followed by measuring isotopic ratios in the Stable Isotope Laboratory for Environmental
161 Research (SILVER) at the University of Vienna. Calculation of the amount of incorporated
162 isotopes was done according to Lintner et al. (2021). Two-way ANOVAs (level of significance
163 $p = 0.05$) were run to test if the type of pesticide, the concentration and/or incubation time
164 significantly affected uptake of ^{15}N and ^{13}C , respectively. Significant results were further
165 analysed for group differences using Tukey's post-hoc test (level of significance $p = 0.05$).

166

167 **3. Results**

168 3.1. Photosynthetic performance of the symbionts

169 The study found that the photosynthetic area of foraminifera was affected by the type ($p <$
170 0.001) and concentration of pesticides used ($p < 0.001$), as well as the incubation time ($p =$
171 0.001). The results showed that the photosynthetic area decreased as the amount of
172 pesticide added increased and as the incubation time increased. The combined effects of
173 pesticide and time also had an impact on the photosynthetic area ($p = 0.048$; Fig. 1).

174 Lowest concentration of the insecticide Confidor had no measurable impact on the
175 photosynthetic performance of the symbionts (see Table 1). At the intermediate
176 concentration, the activity of the symbionts was comparable to the control till day 3 but
177 then decreased by 25% for during the next 9 days. The highest concentration applied had
178 strong negative impacts, with the photosynthetic area decreasing by 90% towards the end
179 of the experiment.

180 For the fungicide Pronto Plus, the symbionts coped well (similar photosynthetic activity
181 compared to the control group) with the lowest concentration of 0.0001% or were even
182 stimulated (slightly higher photosynthetic activity as the control group) at this level.
183 However, the photosynthetic area of the symbionts responded highly sensitively to higher
184 amendment levels, dropping close to zero at the intermediate and high concentrations after
185 one day, respectively.

186 Over the first five days, the amendment of the herbicide Roundup caused a reduction of the
187 photosynthetic area in all foraminifera (total reduction to zero in 1%, reduction by half in
188 0.01% and slightly reduction by 10% in 0.0001%), independent of concentration. Afterwards,
189 the photosynthetic performance of the foraminifera at the lowest concentration recovered
190 in comparison to the beginning of the experiment. However, the performance of the
191 foraminifera at the intermediate concentration decreased from day 1 onwards, reaching a
192 photosynthetic area of zero after 14 days. At the highest concentration, the photosynthetic
193 performance of the symbionts decreased rapidly after one day and reached zero after three
194 days.

195 3.2. Isotope uptake experiments

196 Foraminiferal ¹³C uptake was significantly reduced at the highest pesticide concentration
197 compared to the control ($p < 0.001$). The herbicide and fungicide showed comparable
198 reductions of ¹³C uptake ($p = 0.945$), the reduction caused by the insecticide was less
199 pronounced.

200 The effect of pesticides on the uptake of ¹⁵N by foraminifera was not as clear as that of ¹³C.
201 The type of pesticide had a highly significant impact on the uptake of ¹⁵N ($p < 0.001$). Tukey's
202 post-hoc tests showed that the control group and the insecticide (Confidor) group did not
203 differ significantly in terms of ¹⁵N uptake ($p = 0.950$). The herbicide and fungicide also
204 showed similar reductions in the uptake of ¹⁵N ($p = 0.234$).

205 At low pesticide concentrations, a linear decrease of the ¹³C uptake was detected (Figure
206 2). However, these effects were less pronounced. Meanwhile, in certain instances where
207 low levels of pesticides were applied (such as Roundup), ¹⁵N uptake increased ($p = 0.004$),
208 while in other cases (like Confidor), it had no impact on the uptake ($p = 0.950$) compared to
209 the control group.

210

211 **4. Discussion**

212 4.1. Effects of pesticides on foraminifera

213 For foraminifera, which build their calcite tests, inorganic carbon fluxes and metabolism are
214 of utmost importance (e.g., Tyszka et al., 2021). Their photosymbionts rely heavily on
215 inorganic carbon supply for photosynthetic fixation. If inorganic carbon supply is reduced or
216 inhibited, the symbionts will not be able to provide the foraminifera with photoassimilates
217 such as carbohydrates (Hallock, 2000). Our study reveals that even low concentrations of
218 pesticides can lead to reduced inorganic carbon uptake, causing a rapid and significant
219 decrease in the uptake by foraminifera.

220 It is important to note that we have only studied one species of LBF, not the whole
221 foraminifera community. As a result, we cannot calculate the FORAM index (Hallock et al.,
222 2003) for the presence of pesticides at this time. However, based on our knowledge, we
223 assume that seawater containing pesticides leads to a reduction in the population of LBF,
224 which in turn causes a drop in the FORAM index. Gupta et al. (2003) assumed that pesticides
225 have a negative effect on foraminiferal abundance and diversity comparable to heavy metal
226 pollution, but they did not investigate the impact in detail. A few years later, researchers
227 observed foraminifera with increased abnormalities in their tests in regions with elevated
228 pesticide concentrations (Gabriella et al., 2009; Jayaraju and Reddy, 2008). During our
229 experiments, we did not detect any deformities, which however can be explained by the
230 short exposure time and the age of the individuals. We study adult specimens, which did not
231 build new chambers during the 14 days.

232 Recent studies have shown that the seawater of Indonesia contains around 120 ng L⁻¹ of
233 organochlorine pesticides (Khozanah, et al., 2022); 77-387 ng pesticides (cyanazine,
234 simetryn, fenarimol, isoprothiolane, diazinon, irgarol, fenitrothion, and diuron) per g
235 sediment (dry mass) were measured at the coast of Japan (Chidya et al., 2022). These values
236 are similar to the pesticide contents provided in the studies by Shaw et al. (2010) and Lewis
237 et al. (2009), which suggest that pesticides have been accumulating in seawater over the
238 last few decades. The concentrations in the studies mentioned above are around a factor of
239 10 smaller than the lowest concentration we tested, but there are concerns that pesticide

240 concentrations in the sea will increase soon due to climatic changes (Ukhurebor et al.,
241 2020). Another point to note is that the studies mentioned above always measure the active
242 substances of the pesticide in the environment and we have considered the total pesticides.
243 As already mentioned in the methods section, Roundup© only contains 1% glyphosate. In
244 Pronto©Plus the active substance tebuconazole has 13.6% and in Confidor© the
245 imidacloprid concentration is 20%, according to the manufacturer's information. Based on
246 that, the concentration of active pesticides substances, which can be found in the
247 environment are not a factor of 10 smaller than ours tested, they are approximately the
248 same concentration or even 10 times higher. Current studies indicate that bad weather
249 conditions such as storms or floods can release bound pesticides from sediment, causing
250 them to enter the ocean water column (Concha-Graña et al., 2022). Moreover, pesticides
251 can adhere to plastic particles and are therefore protected from hydrolysis (Concha-Graña
252 et al., 2022). Together with increasing pollution from plastic particles, this poses a serious
253 risk because pesticides will remain in the sediment for long periods and also accumulated
254 there. Future studies should investigate which foraminifera species can tolerate these
255 pollutants and to what extent. For this reason, it is important to test also higher
256 concentrations of pesticides on foraminifera, as we did in our study. Our results show that
257 *Heterostegina depressa* is particularly sensitive to the presence of pesticides. This species is
258 likely to disappear when pesticide concentrations are around 0.01% (0.1 g L⁻¹), which is
259 much higher than those currently found in seawater. From the experiments, we conclude
260 that *H. depressa* is found only in habitats with pesticides concentration less than 0.01%.

261

262 4.2. Impact of pesticides on the host-symbiont system

263 If isotope uptake is compared with the PAM fluorescence results, some differences can be
264 observed, which we attribute to the varying effects of pesticides on the foraminifera host
265 and on the symbiont. Lintner et al. (2023) proved that the uptake and assimilation of certain
266 compounds such as carbonate or nitrate are strongly controlled by the symbiont, while
267 other compounds such as glucose or ammonium are more likely to be assimilated by the
268 foraminiferal host.

269 Confidor® is an insecticide used in tropical and temperate regions for fruit and vegetable
270 production (<https://www.bayer.com/en/id/confidor>). The active substance in Confidor® is
271 Imidacloprid, a neonicotinoid compound with systemic effects on insects. It is contained at a
272 concentration of 200 g L⁻¹ in the stock solution. Imidacloprid has low mammalian toxicity
273 and mainly affects phytophagous insects (Mullins, 1993). Imidacloprid in seawater did not
274 have a negative effect on aquatic vertebrates, but showed toxicity on microalgae (Tišler et
275 al., 2009). Similar to Tišler et al.'s results, especially the increased concentrations of
276 Confidor® noticeably reduced the activity of the symbionts or led to the death of the algae
277 within a few days. The uptake and assimilation of inorganic carbon also decreased with
278 increasing concentrations of Confidor®, suggesting the disruption of the activity of the
279 symbionts finally resulting in algal death. *Heterostegina*, which obligatorily hosts
280 photosymbionts, will also die as a result.

281 Pronto®Plus is a fungicide with the active ingredients Tebuconazole (stock solution 133 g L⁻¹)
282 and Spiroxamine (250 g L⁻¹; <https://www.adama-produkte.com/de/produkt/pronto-plus>).
283 Tebuconazole, a triazole, and spiroxamine, a spiroketalamine, both inhibit fungal sterol
284 biosynthesis. Tebuconazole is applied to reduce fungal infestation on cereals, but it is also
285 applied in rice cultivation (Scheuermann et al., 2021). Tebuconazole can have negative
286 effects on aquatic organisms, since increased concentrations lead to oxidative stress (Toni et
287 al., 2011). If applied for a longer time, it can accumulate in fish tissues thus entering the
288 human food chain (Toni et al., 2011). Our results showed that Pronto®Plus was highly toxic
289 to both, the host and the symbiont, even at the lowest concentrations provided.

290 Photosynthetically active area and carbon uptake were reduced to zero after just 24 hours
291 exposure time, which indicates that the algae died immediately after the first contact with
292 the fungicide. Unlike the experiments with Confidor®, contact with Pronto®Plus also
293 significantly reduced host nitrogen uptake, which suggests that both, symbionts and the
294 foraminiferal hosts are negatively affected.

295 Roundup® is an herbicide that is used to eliminate weeds (source: <https://roundup.com>).
296 The primary active ingredient in Roundup is glyphosate, which has been in commercial use
297 since 1974 (Duke, 2018). Glyphosate is a phosphonate that inhibits an enzyme in the
298 shikimic acid pathway, which is responsible for producing aromatic amino acids that are
299 necessary for protein synthesis and plant growth (Carlisle and Trevors, 1988). Despite its

300 long residence time in soil, glyphosate continues to be used frequently. Researchers are
301 currently working on reducing glyphosate levels in soils and developing methods for
302 detecting trace amounts using nanoparticles (for example, Chang et al., 2023). In 2015,
303 Avigliano et al. reported glyphosate concentrations as high as 1,600 µg/L in seawater in
304 Argentina, corresponding to roughly 0.16%. Studies on marine phytoplankton have shown
305 that different algal species respond differently to glyphosate (Wang et al., 2016). Some
306 algae may even be able to use glyphosate as a source of phosphorus, while other species
307 experience impaired growth at very low concentrations (Wang et al., 2016). Our study found
308 that diatoms living as symbionts in *H. depressa* were negatively impacted by Roundup
309 treatment. Within a few days, both the photosynthetically active area and inorganic carbon
310 uptake dropped to zero. However, nitrogen uptake remained constant or even increased
311 slightly, suggesting that the foraminiferal host remained active for a short time, despite the
312 symbiont dying almost immediately, similar to the effect of the pesticide Confidor®.

313

314 **5. Conclusions**

315 The study aimed to investigate the impact of the three widely used pesticides Confidor®,
316 Pronto®Plus, and Roundup® on the metabolism and the activity of the marine foraminifera
317 *Heterostegina depressa* and their symbionts. This species is of particular interest due to its
318 obligatory symbionts, which enable researchers to study mutual interactions. The study
319 found that even low concentrations of pesticides can have a negative impact on the
320 metabolism of marine organisms. This applies not only to the foraminiferal host but also to
321 their symbionts. By examining differences in nitrogen and carbon uptake, the study showed
322 that the here tested fungicide Pronto®Plus is toxic to both the host and its symbiont,
323 whereas the herbicide Roundup® and insecticide Confidor® mainly have negative effects
324 on the symbionts. However, as the symbionts are obligatory, symbiont death (bleaching)
325 ultimately leads also to the death of the foraminifera. Already today, climate change leads
326 to heavy storms and heavy rainfall along coastal areas, which together with increased use of
327 pesticides due to intensive agriculture, may lead to a significant increase in pesticide
328 concentrations in the sea in the near future. We were able to show that this negative effect
329 on pesticides can be observed on foraminifera. It is also present in corals and other
330 organisms hosting obligatory phototrophic protist symbionts. In conclusion, the discharge of

331 pesticides into the sea can have severe negative impacts on foraminifera, even at low
332 concentrations, making these compounds a serious threat to the health of marine reefs.

333

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340

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571 Table 1: Two way-ANOVA testing the effects of exposure time and concentration of pesticides and their interaction on ¹³C and on ¹⁵N
572 uptake by the foraminifera (n=6, df = degree of freedom, significant values are in bold).

pesticide	isotope	factor	df	F	p
Confidor	C	time	3	27.29	<0.001
	C	conc.	1	15.65	<0.001
	C	interaction	3	1.819	0.159
	N	time	3	12.48	<0.001
	N	conc.	1	0.002	0.969
	N	interaction	3	2.158	0.108
ProntoPlus	C	time	3	0.207	0.891
	C	conc.	1	44.91	<0.001
	C	interaction	3	0.192	0.901
	N	time	3	26.78	<0.001
	N	conc.	1	74.56	<0.001
	N	interaction	3	25.64	<0.001
Round UP	C	time	3	4.616	0.007
	C	conc.	1	95.48	<0.001

C	interaction	3	4.739	0.006
N	time	3	9.946	<0.001
N	conc.	1	30.00	<0.001
N	interaction	3	4.372	0.009

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Fig.1: Results of the incubation experiments with different pesticides at various concentrations over two weeks. Shortcuts are: PP = Pronto Plus, RU = Round UP, Conf = Confidor; photosynthetic active area of treatments was standardized to that one of controls (n = 6). Active substances in the pesticides: 1% glyphosate in Roundup®, 13.6% tebuconazole in Pronto®Plus and 20% imidacloprid in Confidor®.

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581 Fig.2: Results of the isotopic incubation experiments with different pesticides at two concentrations over two weeks. Abbreviations are: PP

582 = Pronto©Plus, RU = Roundup©, and Conf = Confidor©. IC and IN stands for the incorporated amount of carbon (IC) and nitrogen (IN)

583 during the incubation (n=6, error bars show the standard error). Active substances in the pesticides: 1% glyphosate in Roundup©, 13.6%

584 tebuconazole in Pronto©Plus and 20% imidacloprid in Confidor©.